

THE ROLE OF INNOVATIVE ACTIVITY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF MEDIA CULTURE OF PRESCHOOL TEACHER

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Abstract. *In this article, the step-by-step forms and ways of developing the media culture of educators of preschool education organizations are fully covered, and it includes many issues that develop the field of preschool education.*

Keywords: *innovation, technology, method, kasib competence, first step, program, creativity, interactive.*

New reforms in the field of education in our country require a new approach and preparation for the renewal process from every pedagogue. In the address to the people of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in the development of the field of education and science, the task is to increase the coverage of preschool education organizations in all regions and to develop new programs and projects for the construction and reconstruction of preschool education organizations that are convenient for children. determined. Based on the new decisions, the separation of preschool education and the Ministry of Education and reforms in the field of preschool education have become the most important and urgent issues of today.

Innovative, i.e. renewal ideas are a unique social necessity of society's development and include approaches that are not used in science and production. One-sided approaches to renewal processes are observed in modern pedagogy. In particular, there is a tradition of considering the ideas of pedagogical renewal as related to the organizational forms of education, age, methods and styles.

As in all fields, the process of innovative approach to the education system is observed in the field of preschool education. So, what are the forms of innovation?

Innovations are manifested in the following forms:

New ideas;

Specific goals aimed at changing the system or direction of activity;

Non-traditional approaches;

Unusual initiatives;

advanced working methods;

As we know, innovative activity is the introduction of innovation into the process of education. The stages of innovative activity: establishing a new idea or concept, creating something new, applying the created innovation in practice, widely implementing the innovation, ensuring the dominance of innovation in a certain field. Therefore, it is possible to achieve the most effective results of improving the media culture of educators through innovative activities.

Types of innovative activities in the preschool education organization:

1. Separation of the most advanced methods in the field of preschool education;

2. Innovative approach to the method or method and perception, reduction and evaluation;

3. Establish activities based on medical literacy at the stages of using the innovation and its introduction.

Nowadays, new pedagogical technologies and innovations are rapidly entering the system of public education. Educators do not use these innovations enough in their activities, because most of the young educators have a very low level of media literacy. This remains one of the major problems in the field of preschool education.

Any innovative changes in the field of preschool education, the introduction of innovations into the educational system are carried out directly by updating and changing the activity of educators. This activity of the educator also goes back to media culture and can be an example of innovative activity based on media literacy.

Innovative activity based on media literacy is a process with subjective and objective factors that lead to the result of creativity and creative activity of the educator, high professionalism, and a long creative life of the specialist.

The educator's media literacy, ability to create innovative activities and create new models are manifested in the following features:

Fluency of thought;

To be able to direct the opinion according to the purpose;

Individuality;

Curiosity;

The ability to create hypotheses;

Being able to imagine;

As criteria for the educator's readiness for innovative activities aimed at improving media literacy:

Understanding the need for innovative activities that increase media literacy;

Let's prepare to be involved in creative activities that increase professional competence;

Aligning personal goals with innovative activities that increase media literacy;

Preparation for overcoming creative failures;

Increase the level of technological preparation for the implementation of innovative activities aimed at the development of media literacy;

Expanding the influence of media literacy-increasing innovation activities on professional independence;

It should be noted that the innovative activities that increase media literacy are based on pedagogical technologies, and today it is clear to everyone that they cannot be used separately from information and communication technologies.

A scientific and innovative approach to raising the level of educators in the process of qualification improvement, providing them with practical assistance, discussing current issues in the process of activity, popularizing advanced work practices, and increasing the effectiveness of education through the introduction of pedagogical and information technologies into the educational process. is required. Educators should have psychological, pedagogical, technological knowledge and media literacy, not just in their field.

Implementation of current issues in the field of education largely depends on the personality of the educator. Achieving the intended goal of education, organizing activities of educators, carrying out education and upbringing at the same time in the process of activity, and

raising educated, polite, faithful, hardworking, business-minded, well-rounded. assigned to the educator.

The media literacy of the educator largely depends on the following:

It is necessary for a modern teacher to be aware of the news and achievements of science, technology and technology,

Educator should have deep and thorough knowledge of his specialty;

The educator should be able to deeply understand the nature of the changes taking place in society and social life, the social reforms being carried out, and be able to provide correct and reasonable information to the educated in this regard;

Educator should be able to effectively use the most effective forms, methods, tools in the process of activity;

An educator can develop creativity, initiative and organizational skills;

Educator should have speech culture;

Educator's dressing culture should be unique;

The teacher should be pure in his personal life and be an example to others;

To have the knowledge to use information technologies correctly;

Ability to use innovative ideas in the process of activity.

Media literacy mainly serves to bring the training to an interactive point. Media literacy helps to increase the effectiveness of the training process. The main criteria of media literacy are: conducting informal discussions, the ability to freely describe and express the educational material, the teacher's speech is small, but the number of interesting activities is large, the students take the initiative. It is important to create opportunities for them to show, to give tasks to work in small groups, large groups, and teams, in increasing the effectiveness of educational work.

Based on the information given above, we can conclude that the innovative activity of the educator aimed at developing media literacy helps to increase his professional competence and creative approach to his work. Makes his work easier and instills love for his profession. This has a positive effect on the expansion of its scope of work and the quality of education.

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